

KIDNEYS AT DIFFERENT STAGES IN CHEMICAL BURNS OF THE DIGESTIVE TRACT COMPARATIVE DESCRIPTION OF MORPHOMETRIC CHANGES

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Relevance of the topic: In recent decades, 2-3 cases of poisoning per 1,000 children are recorded in Russia and Western European countries, and children are the 4th in terms of the number of deaths from chemical poisoning from injuries, burns, and drowning. takes the place and exceeds the general indicator. number of deaths from childhood infections About 3% of hospitalizations for children are related to poisoning with various chemicals and drugs Wide use of chemicals and drugs that have a nephrotoxic effect, cause hemodynamic disturbances and have a direct negative effect on the organs of the urinary system can lead to various levels of functional state of the kidneys.

Often, both in children and in adult patients, toxic damage to the kidney is accompanied by the development of acute kidney injury (AKI). OBY, including nephrotoxic effects, plays a leading role in the development of permanent kidney dysfunction in children of various ages and often determines the prognosis. In case of poisoning, the incidence of nephropathy reaches 30%, and many toxic substances directly Since it has a nephrotoxic effect, a small concentration may be enough for a child to develop toxic nephropathy.

Toxic nephropathy is a non-inflammatory disease caused by acute exogenous intoxication, characterized by damage to the entire nephron system and impaired filtration, secretion, and reabsorption functions. Toxic kidney damage is characterized by acute and chronic interstitial nephritis, glomerulonecrosis, tubular necrosis, as well as acute kidney injury, including acute renal failure.

It is known that the kidney is one of the main responsible organs in the body. The main function of the kidney is to remove decomposed toxins from the body. In case of chemical burns, gastrointestinal and respiratory tracts may be burned as a result of accidental or suicidal use of the substance. The circumstances of the incident and the chemical nature of the substance determine the level of damage and toxicological risk. The initial period after a chemical burn is laryngeal swelling, redness Perforation of the stomach, intestines, gastrointestinal bleeding and pancreatitis are associated with the possibility of acute kidney failure.

Acetic acid is a characteristic colorless liquid highly volatile compound. It dissolves inside heavier than water. Vapors ignite very quickly and form explosive mixtures. diluted acetic acid, available acid - 40-90%, table vinegar - 3-8%. 70% solution of acetic acid is used in everyday life in the food industry in Uzbekistan.

The most common causes of death in patients are exotoxic shock, early gastrointestinal bleeding, as well as the development of acute renal failure against a heavy background, late hemoglobinuric nephrosis

Consequences of poisoning include retrograde changes in the oral cavity, esophagus, urinary system, stomach or respiratory system. In addition, it can lead to the formation of strictures in the organs. Stricture formation can have serious systemic consequences for the patient,

including poor general condition, significant weight loss, malnutrition, recurrent aspiration leading to respiratory infections, and potential respiratory failure.

The degree of study of the problem. Acute poisoning with acetic acid is one of the leading causes of chemical burns of the alimentary canal. Poisoning in Russia is characterized by a high mortality rate (6-17%) of hospitalized patients. confirms. According to the American Association of Poison Control Centers, more than 1.6 million children were poisoned in 2008 alone.

Many aspects of acetic acid poisoning are well-studied. The severity of acetic acid poisoning is determined by the degree of damage to internal organs, which is associated with the specific effect of acetic acid (hemoglobinuric nephrosis against the background of intravascular hemolysis of erythrocytes) and exotoxic shock. The most important morphofunctional changes are observed in parenchymal organs (lungs, liver, spleen, kidneys), their damage mainly determines the clinical appearance and severity of the disease in the acute period of poisoning.

Summary. White outbred rats have different d in chemical burns of the alimentary canal.

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